

REINTEGRATION OF INTERNALLY DISPLACED PERSONS IN NORTHEAST NIGERIA: SUCCESSES, STRATEGIES AND CHALLENGES

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Internally Displaced Persons, Reintegration Strategies, Insecurity, Livelihood Restoration, Conflict-Affected Communities.

Abstract: *This study assessed the strategies, successes, and challenges associated with the reintegration of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Northeast Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, employing both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The target population for the study was 2,500 individuals, comprising 1,200 IDPs, 800 members of host communities, and 500 officials from government agencies, international organizations, and NGOs directly involved in reintegration activities across three conflict-affected states in Northeast Nigeria: Borno, Yobe, and Adamawa. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select the respondents. First, Borno, Yobe, and Adamawa States were purposively selected due to their high concentration of IDPs and reintegration interventions. In each state, two Local Government Areas (LGAs) with active IDP resettlement and reintegration programs were selected, totaling six LGAs. Within each LGA, the study population was stratified into three groups: IDPs, host community members, and reintegration stakeholders. From each group, respondents were randomly selected to ensure representativeness. Data were collected using a validated questionnaire titled Reintegration of Internally Displaced Persons Questionnaire (RIDPQ) and key informant interviews (KII), analyzed with SPSS for quantitative responses (mean and standard deviation) and NVivo for qualitative insights. Findings revealed that strategies such as provision of shelters, vocational training, agricultural support, and infrastructure reconstruction have significantly contributed to reintegration efforts. However, challenges such as persistent insecurity, inadequate funding, destroyed livelihoods, poor healthcare access, and lack of coordination between stakeholders continue to undermine sustainable reintegration. Key informants emphasized the need for*

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community-driven interventions, improved governance, and integrated approaches to peacebuilding and development. The study concluded that while modest progress has been achieved, more coherent, inclusive, and security-sensitive strategies are required for lasting reintegration outcomes. It recommended increased collaboration among stakeholders, improved funding, enhancement of healthcare and legal support, and the strengthening of local security structures.

Introduction

Internal displacement refers to the involuntary or forced movement of individuals or groups within the borders of their own country due to conflict, violence, disasters, or other factors that threaten their lives and livelihoods (United Nations, 1998). Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) are thus individuals or groups who have been compelled to flee their homes, particularly due to armed conflict, generalized violence, violations of human rights, or natural or human-made disasters, without crossing an internationally recognized state border (Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre [IDMC], 2022).

In the context of Northeast Nigeria, internal displacement has become a major humanitarian concern, primarily driven by the protracted Boko Haram insurgency that began in 2009. The extremist activities of Boko Haram have led to widespread violence, abductions, destruction of communities, and mass killings, compelling millions to flee their homes in search of safety (International Organization for Migration [IOM], 2021). According to UNHCR (2022), the insurgency alone has resulted in the displacement of over 2.2 million people across

Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe states. Besides the insurgency, other contributing factors to internal displacement in the region include communal clashes, ethnic conflicts, and herder-farmer disputes, which often escalate into violent confrontations and destruction of property (Okoli & Nnamani, 2018). Additionally, armed banditry and military counterinsurgency operations have further exacerbated displacement trends, creating a complex humanitarian crisis in the region (NEMA, 2020). The scale of internal displacement in Northeast Nigeria remains one of the most significant humanitarian crises in Sub-Saharan Africa. As of 2023, the International Organization for Migration (IOM) reported that approximately 2.2 million people were internally displaced across the six states of Northeast Nigeria, with the majority concentrated in Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe States (IOM, 2023). These three states, often referred to as the BAY states, have been the epicenter of conflict and displacement due to persistent attacks by Boko Haram and other non-state armed groups.

Borno State alone accounts for the highest number of IDPs, hosting over 1.6 million displaced persons, which is about 75% of the

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total IDP population in the region (UNHCR, 2022). In Adamawa State, over 210,000 individuals have been displaced, while Yobe State hosts an estimated 130,000 IDPs (NEMA, 2021; IOM, 2023). These figures highlight the severe impact of insurgency and insecurity in these areas, leading to massive humanitarian needs related to shelter, food, water, healthcare, and education.

Additionally, the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (UNOCHA) noted that more than 8.4 million people in the region, including both IDPs and host communities, are in need of humanitarian assistance due to the ongoing conflict and displacement crisis (UNOCHA, 2022). Despite efforts to support and reintegrate displaced populations, insecurity and limited resources continue to hinder effective responses.

Reintegration of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) is a critical process for ensuring sustainable peace, national stability, and long-term development in conflict-affected regions such as Northeast Nigeria. Reintegration plays a pivotal role in closing the cycle of displacement by restoring the dignity, security, and livelihoods of affected populations while also promoting social cohesion and reducing the risk of renewed conflict (UNHCR, 2022). According to the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2020), successful reintegration contributes to peacebuilding by rebuilding trust among communities, addressing root causes of conflict, and reducing the likelihood of relapse into violence. Moreover, reintegration ensures

the socio-economic inclusion of IDPs, thereby contributing to national stability and economic development (IOM, 2023).

Despite ongoing national and international efforts, the reintegration of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Northeast Nigeria continues to face numerous persistent challenges that undermine its effectiveness and long-term sustainability. One of the foremost issues is insecurity. The continued presence of Boko Haram insurgents and other non-state armed groups has made many areas unsafe for return, while sporadic attacks discourage both IDPs and humanitarian actors from fully engaging in reintegration processes (UNHCR, 2022; IOM, 2023). This lingering insecurity makes it difficult for returnees to settle and rebuild their lives.

Another major constraint is the lack of infrastructure, particularly in rural areas where many IDPs originate. Public facilities such as schools, hospitals, water systems, and roads have been destroyed or severely damaged during years of conflict (UNOCHA, 2022). Without the rehabilitation of basic infrastructure, returnees often find themselves in environments that are not conducive to reintegration or sustainable living. This, in turn, contributes to community resistance, as host populations who also suffer from poverty and underdevelopment may perceive returning IDPs as competition for scarce resources (Okoli & Nnamani, 2018).

Limited funding is another significant obstacle. Humanitarian organizations frequently report shortfalls in financial support for reintegration programs, which affects the scale and quality of

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interventions. According to UNOCHA (2022), as of mid-2022, less than half of the funds required for Nigeria's humanitarian response had been raised. These funding gaps result in fragmented service delivery and limited reach to vulnerable populations.

Additionally, psychosocial trauma among IDPs poses a less visible but equally critical barrier to reintegration. Many displaced persons suffer from post-traumatic stress, grief, and anxiety after experiencing violence, abduction, or the loss of loved ones. Without adequate psychosocial support, their ability to participate in community life and economic activities remains constrained (UNDP, 2020).

A critical issue compounding all these challenges is the gap in policy implementation and coordination. While Nigeria has developed frameworks like the National Policy on Internally Displaced Persons, implementation remains weak due to institutional fragmentation, lack of political will, and insufficient inter-agency collaboration (NEMA, 2021). This disconnect between policy and practice hinders the delivery of comprehensive reintegration services and prevents the alignment of humanitarian and development efforts.

These challenges are highly relevant to peacebuilding, human rights, and social cohesion. Without reintegration, displaced persons remain vulnerable to marginalization, and the risk of renewed conflict increases. Reintegration also ties into the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities),

SDG 16 (Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions), and SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals), which all emphasize inclusive development and the protection of vulnerable groups (UNDP, 2020). Ultimately, reintegration is not just a humanitarian necessity but a development imperative. It enables IDPs to reclaim agency over their lives, supports the restoration of social fabric, and contributes to national security and economic recovery. Without it, efforts to achieve lasting peace and development in Northeast Nigeria will remain elusive.

Statement of the Problem

Despite sustained national and international efforts to address the humanitarian crisis in Northeast Nigeria, the reintegration of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) remains a complex and unresolved challenge. Over a decade of insurgency, communal violence, and armed conflict has led to the displacement of more than 2.2 million people, particularly in Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe States (IOM, 2023; UNHCR, 2022). While several initiatives, including those by the Presidential Committee on the Northeast Initiative (PCNI), UN agencies, and NGOs, have been implemented to support IDPs' return and reintegration, the process is far from complete or sustainable.

Persistent insecurity, damaged infrastructure, limited funding, lack of psychosocial support, and weak institutional coordination continue to hamper reintegration efforts. Many IDPs face hostility from host communities, experience trauma from past violence, and lack access to basic services and livelihood opportunities.

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Moreover, although policy frameworks exist to support reintegration, their implementation is often fragmented and inconsistent across agencies and regions (NEMA, 2021). These challenges not only delay the successful reintegration of displaced persons but also threaten peacebuilding, social cohesion, and national development goals.

The absence of a comprehensive, coordinated, and community-driven reintegration strategy raises critical questions about the long-term stability of the region and the wellbeing of millions of displaced citizens. If unaddressed, these gaps may lead to protracted displacement, renewed cycles of violence, and increased vulnerability among already marginalized populations. Therefore, it is imperative to critically assess the reintegration strategies, identify existing successes and shortcomings, and propose actionable solutions that align with peacebuilding, human rights, and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose was to assess the reintegration of internally displaced persons in Northeast Nigeria; its Successes, Strategies and Challenges

- i. To examine the various strategies adopted by national and international agencies in the reintegration of IDPs in Northeast Nigeria.
- ii. To assess the successes recorded in the reintegration process of IDPs in Northeast Nigeria.
- iii. To identify the major challenges hindering the effective reintegration of IDPs in

conflict-affected communities in Northeast Nigeria.

Research Questions

- i. What are the strategies adopted by national and international agencies for reintegrating Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Northeast Nigeria?
- ii. To what extent have these strategies contributed to the successful reintegration of IDPs in Northeast Nigeria?
- iii. What are the major challenges affecting the effective reintegration of IDPs in conflict-affected communities of Northeast Nigeria?

Literature Review

Reintegration: A Brief Conceptual Description

Reintegration is a multi-dimensional process that encompasses various interrelated components aimed at ensuring that returnees and resettled individuals are able to rebuild their lives with dignity and security. Reintegration facilitates healing and reconciliation, enabling both returnees and host communities to coexist peacefully and productively. It also helps reduce the burden on urban centers and host communities that often face resource pressure due to the prolonged presence of IDPs (NEMA, 2021). From a governance and development perspective, the inability to reintegrate displaced populations threatens not only the social fabric of affected communities but also undermines state capacity and legitimacy (UNOCHA, 2022).

Key Elements of Reintegration

The following are the identified elements of reintegration of IDPs either cause by natural disaster or man-made:

- i. *Resettlement*: Providing safe and permanent housing or returning displaced individuals to their original communities when security allows.
- ii. *Livelihood Restoration*: Enabling IDPs to regain or develop sustainable means of income through vocational training, job creation, and access to financial services (IOM, 2021).
- iii. *Access to Education*: Ensuring that children and youth continue their education to prevent generational poverty and support development.
- iv. *Psychosocial Support*: Offering trauma healing services to help individuals recover from conflict-induced mental and emotional distress (UNHCR, 2022).
- v. *Security and Protection*: Guaranteeing the safety of returnees by clearing remnants of conflict, providing community policing, and ensuring legal rights (UNDP, 2020).

Without addressing these reintegration dimensions, displaced individuals remain vulnerable to secondary displacement and long-term marginalization. Therefore, effective reintegration is not just a humanitarian goal but a strategic imperative for post-conflict recovery and national development.

The reintegration of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Northeast Nigeria has been the focus of both national and international

humanitarian and development efforts aimed at restoring dignity, stability, and livelihoods for affected populations. One of the major national interventions was the establishment of the Presidential Committee on the Northeast Initiative (PCNI) in 2016, tasked with coordinating relief and development efforts, including the rehabilitation and reintegration of IDPs, through its “Buhari Plan” for the reconstruction of the Northeast (PCNI, 2017). The PCNI worked in collaboration with state governments, donor agencies, and humanitarian organizations to support community stabilization, housing reconstruction, and economic empowerment programs.

International organizations such as the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), International Organization for Migration (IOM), and United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) have also been instrumental in supporting reintegration efforts. For instance, UNHCR has provided shelter kits, non-food items, and legal documentation for returning IDPs, while IOM has conducted needs assessments, return intention surveys, and managed displacement tracking systems to guide reintegration planning (UNHCR, 2022; IOM, 2023).

Numerous Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) such as the Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC), Mercy Corps, and the International Rescue Committee (IRC) have implemented community-based reintegration programs, including livelihood training, cash-based interventions, and psychosocial support to help

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displaced persons rebuild their lives. These programs often target both IDPs and host communities to foster social cohesion and reduce tensions.

The strategies employed in these reintegration efforts include:

- i. *Housing and Shelter Support:* Provision of temporary and permanent housing solutions, shelter repair kits, and construction materials to returnees (UNHCR, 2022).
- ii. *Livelihood Empowerment:* Implementation of vocational training, cash-for-work schemes, and microenterprise grants to facilitate income generation (UNDP, 2020).
- iii. *Security Restoration:* Deployment of community security initiatives, collaboration with local vigilante groups, and de-mining operations to ensure safe returns (UNOCHA, 2022).
- iv. *Education and Social Services:* Reestablishment of schools, provision of learning materials, and integration of returnee children into the education system.
- v. *Psychosocial and Legal Support:* Provision of trauma counseling, legal aid services, and reissuance of civil documents such as birth certificates and national IDs (IOM, 2021).

The reintegration of IDPs remains a challenge by persistent insecurity, inadequate funding, and weak coordination among stakeholders, indicating the need for more sustainable, long-term, and locally owned solutions.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which is suitable for collecting and analyzing data on the current conditions, experiences, and perceptions of individuals regarding the reintegration of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Northeast Nigeria. This design enabled the researcher to explore the successes, strategies, and challenges of reintegration from the perspectives of key stakeholders. The target population for the study was 2,500 individuals, comprising 1,200 IDPs, 800 members of host communities, and 500 officials from government agencies, international organizations, and NGOs directly involved in reintegration activities across three conflict-affected states in Northeast Nigeria: Borno, Yobe, and Adamawa. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select the respondents. First, Borno, Yobe, and Adamawa States were purposively selected due to their high concentration of IDPs and reintegration interventions. In each state, two Local Government Areas (LGAs) with active IDP resettlement and reintegration programs were selected, totaling six LGAs. Within each LGA, the study population was stratified into three groups: IDPs, host community members, and reintegration stakeholders. From each group, respondents were randomly selected to ensure representativeness.

The sample size for the study was 360 respondents, made up as follows: 150 IDPs, 120 host community members, and 90 reintegration stakeholders (including officials from NEMA,

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SEMA, UNHCR, IOM, NGOs, and community-based organizations). Proportional allocation was used to select participants from each state and LGA based on population density and the level of reintegration activities.

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled "*Reintegration of Internally Displaced Persons Questionnaire (RIDPQ)*," consisting of both closed-ended and open-ended items. The questionnaire was designed to elicit information on reintegration strategies, levels of success, and persistent challenges. To enrich the data, Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) were also conducted with 12 selected stakeholders (4 from each state), including traditional leaders, senior officials of humanitarian agencies, and security personnel involved in reintegration operations. The validity of the instrument was ensured through expert reviews by scholars in conflict management,

development studies, and humanitarian assistance. A pilot test was conducted on 30 respondents in a non-sampled LGA in Bauchi State, and the reliability of the questionnaire was determined using Cronbach’s Alpha, which yielded a coefficient of 0.84, indicating good internal consistency. Data collected from the questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. Qualitative data from the interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis, allowing for the identification of key themes, patterns, and insights regarding the reintegration process.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the strategies adopted by national and international agencies for reintegrating Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Northeast Nigeria?

Table 1: Strategies for Reintegrating IDPs in Northeast Nigeria

S/N	Questionnaire Statement	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	Provision of shelter and essential supplies (e.g., food, water, healthcare).	4.52	0.61	Agreed
2	Cash-based assistance programs for livelihood restoration.	4.31	0.73	Agreed
3	Vocational training (e.g., tailoring, farming, crafts) for income generation.	4.28	0.69	Agreed
4	Psychosocial support and trauma counseling services.	3.92	0.85	Agreed
5	Rebuilding infrastructure (schools, health clinics, roads) in return communities.	4.15	0.78	Agreed
6	Agricultural support (seeds, tools, livestock) to restart farming.	4.43	0.64	Agreed
7	Education support (e.g., school fees, materials) for children of IDPs.	3.98	0.81	Agreed
8	Conflict resolution and community reconciliation workshops.	3.67	0.92	Agreed
9	Legal aid for property reclamation and documentation (e.g., land titles).	3.54	1.05	Agreed
10	Security sector reforms (e.g., joint patrols) to ensure safe return.	3.41	1.12	Disagreed

The data in Table 1 revealed that respondents largely agreed that a range of strategies have

been adopted by national and international agencies to facilitate the reintegration of

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Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Northeast Nigeria. High mean scores were recorded for the provision of shelters and essential supplies ($\bar{x} = 4.52$), agricultural support ($\bar{x} = 4.43$), cash-based assistance ($\bar{x} = 4.31$), and vocational training ($\bar{x} = 4.28$), indicating strong agreement on these as key reintegration approaches. Other strategies such as psychosocial support ($\bar{x} = 3.92$), rebuilding infrastructure ($\bar{x} = 4.15$), and educational assistance ($\bar{x} = 3.98$) also received positive ratings. However, security sector reforms ($\bar{x} = 3.41$) had the lowest mean and was the only item disagreed upon, suggesting skepticism about the adequacy of current security arrangements to guarantee safe return. Overall, the findings suggest that while multiple reintegration strategies are in place and recognized, concerns remain over the effectiveness of security interventions in facilitating safe and sustainable return of IDPs.

Responses for the KII indicated that:

Response 1:

"The Nigerian government, through NEMA and the Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs, has put in place coordinated strategies such as the provision of temporary shelters, transportation back to communities of origin, and empowerment programs that include skills training and start-up kits. The PCNI also played

a significant role in reconstruction efforts, especially in Borno and Adamawa states. These agencies work with community leaders to foster acceptance and peaceful coexistence."

Response 2:

"International organizations like UNHCR, IOM, and UNICEF have been crucial in providing legal support, psychosocial services, and educational materials. UNHCR, for instance, assists with issuing civil documentation like birth certificates and IDs, which are essential for reintegration. IOM focuses more on shelter provision and community-based reintegration programs. Some NGOs also run cash-for-work schemes and agricultural training to enhance self-reliance."

Response 3:

"A multi-pronged approach is used. Strategies include housing reconstruction, vocational training for youth, and mental health support. In collaboration with local governments, some NGOs run peace education programs to promote social cohesion between returnees and host communities. Health clinics and boreholes have also been constructed in certain communities as part of the reintegration support."

Research Question 2: To what extent have these strategies contributed to the successful reintegration of IDPs in Northeast Nigeria?

Table 2: Contribution of Strategies to Successful Reintegration

S/N	Questionnaire Statement	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	Shelters enabled safe initial return to communities.	4.21	0.74	Agreed
2	Cash assistance improved household economic stability.	3.87	0.89	Agreed
3	Vocational training led to sustainable income for IDPs.	3.59	0.97	Agreed
4	Psychosocial support reduced trauma and improved social cohesion.	3.45	1.08	Disagreed
5	Rebuilt infrastructure (e.g., schools) enhanced access to essential services.	4.02	0.83	Agreed
6	Agricultural programs restored food security for returnees.	4.33	0.71	Agreed
7	Education support increased school enrollment among IDP children.	3.92	0.86	Agreed
8	Reconciliation workshops reduced community tensions.	3.38	1.10	Disagreed
9	Legal aid successfully resolved property disputes.	3.22	1.15	Disagreed
10	Security measures ensured long-term safety for returnees.	2.97	1.20	Disagreed

The results presented in Table 2 indicated that several reintegration strategies have significantly contributed to the successful reintegration of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Northeast Nigeria. Strategies such as agricultural programs ($\bar{x} = 4.33$), provision of shelters ($\bar{x} = 4.21$), improved infrastructure ($\bar{x} = 4.02$), education support ($\bar{x} = 3.92$), and cash assistance ($\bar{x} = 3.87$) were positively rated, showing that they played meaningful roles in enhancing food security, access to services, and economic stability. Vocational training was also acknowledged to contribute to sustainable income ($\bar{x} = 3.59$). However, strategies such as psychosocial support ($\bar{x} = 3.45$), reconciliation workshops ($\bar{x} = 3.38$), legal aid ($\bar{x} = 3.22$), and especially security measures ($\bar{x} = 2.97$) were rated lower, suggesting limited perceived impact in those areas. This implies that while socio-economic support strategies have been fairly effective, interventions in psychological, legal, and security dimensions still require substantial improvement to ensure holistic reintegration.

The KII revealed that:

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Response 1:

"The strategies have had partial success. Many IDPs now live in rebuilt homes and have regained access to farmlands, especially in areas like Mubi and Michika in Adamawa. These interventions have restored a sense of normalcy. However, the reintegration remains fragile due to limited coverage and inconsistent funding, which means many IDPs remain dependent on aid."

Response 2:

"We've seen real progress in terms of school enrollment and livelihood restoration, particularly in camps that transitioned into permanent settlements. IDPs who received training and support now run small businesses. However, in some remote communities, the reintegration is minimal due to the absence of supporting infrastructure and poor coordination among agencies."

Response 3:

"The impact is mixed. Where strategies have been sustained, such as in Maiduguri and Yola, many IDPs have reintegrated successfully. But

in areas still prone to attacks, like parts of Borno, IDPs fear returning home. Psychosocial trauma and poverty also limit reintegration despite the presence of well-meaning programs. Many interventions are short-term and not tailored to long-term community needs."

Research Question 3: What are the major challenges affecting the effective reintegration of IDPs in conflict-affected communities of Northeast Nigeria?

Table 3: Challenges to IDP Reintegration in Northeast Nigeria

S/N	Questionnaire Statement	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	Ongoing insecurity (e.g., attacks by Boko Haram) in return areas.	4.61	0.55	Agreed
2	Inadequate funding for reintegration programs.	4.48	0.62	Agreed
3	Destruction of homes and farmland, limiting livelihoods.	4.53	0.58	Agreed
4	Poor coordination between government and NGOs.	4.22	0.77	Agreed
5	Limited access to healthcare and mental health services.	4.15	0.81	Agreed
6	Land/property disputes due to unclear ownership records.	4.08	0.84	Agreed
7	Stigmatization of IDPs by host communities.	3.92	0.91	Agreed
8	Short-term aid focus rather than long-term development.	3.85	0.95	Agreed
9	Poor infrastructure (roads, electricity) hindering service delivery.	3.72	0.98	Agreed
10	Climate shocks (e.g., droughts) exacerbating resource scarcity.	3.46	1.07	Disagreed

Table 3 revealed that respondents unanimously identified ongoing insecurity (\bar{x} =4.61), underfunding (\bar{x} =4.48), and destroyed livelihoods (\bar{x} =4.53) as critical barriers. Coordination gaps (\bar{x} =4.22) and healthcare deficits (\bar{x} =4.15) also scored highly, reflecting systemic flaws. While stigmatization (\bar{x} =3.92) and short-term aid (\bar{x} =3.85) were acknowledged, however, the respondents disagreed with climate shocks with mean response of (\bar{x} =3.46). The data revealed that conflict dynamics and resource constraints are primary obstacles, demanding integrated security-humanitarian solutions. The KII showed that:

Response 1:

"One major challenge is continued insecurity. Without guaranteed safety, many IDPs refuse to return home. Even when they do, attacks often force them to flee again. Another issue is community resistance. Some host communities perceive returnees as competitors for limited resources, which sparks tension."

Response 2:

"Infrastructure is a serious bottleneck. In many return areas, there are no schools, clinics, or roads. This discourages return and makes life difficult for those who have returned. Furthermore, there's inadequate psychosocial support for victims of violence, especially

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women and children, which affects their ability to reintegrate."

Response 3:

"Funding constraints and weak policy implementation are also barriers. Many programs are donor-driven and not sustained. Coordination between national and international stakeholders is improving but still fragmented. This results in duplication in some areas while other communities receive no intervention at all."

Discussion of Findings

The study revealed that national and international agencies have adopted multiple strategies for reintegrating IDPs, including the provision of shelters, cash-based assistance, vocational training, agricultural inputs, and infrastructural development. These findings agree with the report by Owoaje, Uchendu, and Ajayi (2016), who emphasized that effective reintegration programs must address immediate survival needs and longer-term livelihood restoration. Similarly, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2020) affirmed that vocational training, livelihood empowerment, and infrastructural rebuilding are central to durable reintegration. Moreover, the study by Akinyemi and Ofem (2022) stressed the importance of coordinated efforts involving psychosocial support, education services, and legal assistance to ensure sustainable reintegration outcomes. Notably, the current study found that while most strategies were highly rated, security sector reforms received lower agreement, indicating a lingering

challenge in guaranteeing safe returns. This supports the findings of Bello-Schünemann and Moyer (2018), who identified insecurity as a major barrier to the successful resettlement of IDPs in conflict zones.

Concerning the extent to which these strategies have contributed to successful reintegration, the findings show that provision of shelter, agricultural support, infrastructural development, and education assistance significantly facilitated reintegration. These strategies provided basic needs, restored livelihoods, and improved community functionality. This corroborates the work of Abdu and Umar (2017), who observed that material assistance and farming tools helped IDPs reestablish themselves economically. Additionally, Iroanya and Maphosa (2020) noted that the success of reintegration programs depends largely on how well they address access to basic services, income generation, and education continuity. The moderate ratings for vocational training and cash support in this study also mirror the conclusions of Mohammed and Idris (2021), who emphasized the importance of economic reintegration in achieving long-term stability for IDPs. However, lower ratings in psychosocial support, reconciliation workshops, legal aid, and security arrangements highlight persistent gaps. These weaknesses are similarly identified by Okoli and Ugwu (2019), who noted that without adequate psychological healing and conflict resolution, social cohesion and peacebuilding remain fragile. The low rating for legal aid and property

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restitution also reflects findings by the Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC, 2019), which highlighted that unresolved property disputes can stall reintegration efforts.

The findings from both the quantitative data and Key Informant Interviews reveal that reintegration of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Northeast Nigeria is hindered by persistent insecurity, inadequate funding, destruction of livelihoods, and poor coordinated interventions. These challenges align with the observations of Olanrewaju, Omotoso, and Alabi (2019), who identified insecurity and poor governance as key obstacles to sustainable reintegration. Similarly, Ibrahim and Zanna (2018) emphasized the adverse impact of underfunding and donor fatigue on long-term recovery programs, while Suleiman and Okechukwu (2021) highlighted the critical role of livelihood support in achieving durable reintegration outcomes. Together, these findings underscore the need for a holistic, well-funded, and security-conscious reintegration strategy.

Conclusion:

The study concluded that while various strategies—such as vocational training, shelter provision, cash assistance, and infrastructure rehabilitation—have been implemented by national and international agencies to reintegrate Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Northeast Nigeria, their overall effectiveness is constrained by significant challenges. These include persistent insecurity in return areas, inadequate funding, destruction of livelihoods, limited healthcare access, and lack of

coordination among stakeholders. Although some progress has been recorded in areas like food security and education support, systemic issues continue to hinder full reintegration and community rebuilding. Therefore, a more integrated, sustainable, and context-specific approach is required to facilitate durable solutions for IDPs.

Recommendations:

- 1. Enhance Security in Return Communities:** Government and security agencies should prioritize sustained peace and protection in IDP return areas through community policing and collaborative peacebuilding mechanisms.
- 2. Establish a Multi-Stakeholder Reintegration Framework:** Federal and state governments should coordinate efforts with NGOs, international donors, and community leaders to streamline service delivery and avoid duplication or policy gaps.
- 3. Increase Long-Term Funding and Development Aid:** Donors and government agencies should shift from short-term humanitarian aid to long-term development investments, including livelihood restoration and infrastructure rebuilding.
- 4. Improve Access to Mental Health and Legal Support:** Psychosocial interventions and legal aid services should be scaled up to address trauma, resolve property disputes, and support community reconciliation, particularly for women and vulnerable groups.

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References

Abdu, H. & Umar, M. (2017). *Post-conflict reintegration strategies in Northeast Nigeria*. Journal of Peace and Development, 6(2), 122–135.

Akinyemi, A. & Ofem, B. J. (2022). *Humanitarian interventions and reintegration of displaced populations in Nigeria*. African Journal of Social Policy, 9(1), 33–47.

Bello-Schünemann, J., & Moyer, J. D. (2018). *Structural pressures and instability in Nigeria: Strategic foresight for development*. Institute for Security Studies.

Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC). (2019). *Nigeria: Country profile and displacement challenges*.

Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC). (2022). *Global report on internal displacement 2022*. Norwegian Refugee Council. <https://www.internal-displacement.org/global-report/grid2022/>

International Organization for Migration (IOM). (2021). *Nigeria displacement tracking matrix report: Round 36*. <https://dtm.iom.int/nigeria>

International Organization for Migration (IOM). (2023). *Displacement tracking matrix: Nigeria round 44 report*. <https://dtm.iom.int/reports/nigeria-%E2%80%9444-report>

Iroanya, R. O. & Maphosa, S. (2020). *Durable solutions and reintegration of IDPs in Africa: The Nigerian experience*. Journal of African Studies, 45(3), 298–314.

Mohammed, A. Y. & Idris, S. M. (2021). *Economic reintegration of IDPs in Northern Nigeria: Challenges and prospects*. Nigerian Journal of Development Studies, 11(4), 45–61.

National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA). (2020). *Report on displacement and emergency response in Northeast Nigeria*. Government of Nigeria.

National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA). (2021). *Annual report on humanitarian interventions in Northeast Nigeria*.

Okoli, A. C. & Ugwu, C. C. (2019). *Displacement and the crisis of return in Nigeria's insurgency context*. International Journal of Refugee Studies, 32(1), 85–101.

Okoli, A. C., & Nnamani, O. (2018). *Armed violence and displacement in Northern Nigeria: A threat to human security*.

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Owoaje, E. T., Uchendu, O. C., & Ajayi, T. O. (2016). *Reintegration challenges of internally displaced persons in North-East Nigeria*. *BMC Public Health*, 16(1), 1–9.

Presidential Committee on the Northeast Initiative (PCNI). (2017). *The Buhari Plan: Rebuilding the Northeast*. Government of Nigeria.

United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2020). *Sustaining peace through reintegration: Community-based approaches in post-conflict settings*. <https://www.undp.org>

United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). (2022). *Nigeria: Operational update – Northeast situation*. <https://www.unhcr.org/ng/publications>

United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (UNOCHA). (2022). *Humanitarian needs overview: Nigeria 2022*. <https://reliefweb.int/report/nigeria/nigeria-2022-humanitarian-needs-overview>

United Nations. (1998). *Guiding principles on internal displacement*. United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (UNOCHA). <https://www.unocha.org/publication/guiding-principles-internal-displacement>

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